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Abstract The article provides information on the study of Nurmuhammed Andalib's work in Uzbekistan, who lived and worked in the 18th century. At the same time, the poet's literary heritage should first be realized in the aspect of source studies and textual studies.

Keyword: epic, manuscript, Andalib, ghazal, mukhammas, poet.

Andalib, an Uzbek and Turkmen poet who lived and created in the 18th century and became famous for his beautiful, colorful epics, is a creator who left a significant literary legacy. At the same time, he is also a translator (History of Uzbek literature, 1978, 340).

The real name of the poet is Nurmuhammad, his literary nickname is "Andalib". The word "Andalib" (عندليب) is derived from the Arabic word "Nightingale" (Навоий асарлари луғати, 1972, 50).

Andalib was born in 1711-12 and died in 1770 during the reign of Muhammad Amin Inaq (1770-1791) in Khorezm. There is no information about his life, only through the beginning of the epic "Yusuf and Zulaikha" we can learn that the poet was born in the village of Karamozi in old Urganch and was fifty-five years old when the epic was written.

There were many poets who wrote under the pseudonym "Andalib" in classical literature. V. Abdullayev gives information about this in the third volume of "History of Uzbek literature" (Ўзбек адабиёти тарихи, 1978, 336). At the same time, he also mentioned valuable information about Nurmuhammad Andalib, the author of epics such as "Layli and Majnun", "Yusuf and Zulayha", "Zaynularab".

1960 "Chrestomathy of Uzbek literature" in the second book of the fourth volume, an excerpt from Andalib's epic "Layli and Majnun" is given (Ўзбек адабиёти, 1960, 187-201). "Layli and Majnun" epic is not complete in the publication. Comparative study of this saga with manuscript sources copied during the author's time or in later periods is of great importance.

Information about Andalib's life and activities can be found in the first book of the fifth volume of the 1966 "Chrestomathy of Uzbek literature" (Ўзбек адабиёти, 1966, 103). It contains information about the numbered manuscripts 384, 687 of the poet's epic "Yusuf and Zulaikha" and the numbered 467, 551, 552, 553, 554, 4053, 4054 lithography copies of the poet's epic "Yusuf and Zulaikha" stored in the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

"7054, 6317, 6973, 1107...inventory numbered manuscript bayazs" stored in Institute of Oriental Studies of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan contain Andalib's poems of ghazal, mukhammas, musaddas, rubaiy, musamman and muashshah genres, there is information about naziras attached the ghazals of Navoiy, Fuzuliy, Vafaiy, Ubaydi, Jami and Habibi. But it is written that "the perfect divan of Andalib has not been found yet" (Ўзбек адабиёти, 1966, 104).

One ghazal of Andalib with 7 stanzas is copied in this collection. In addition, in this edition, Andalib's 7-verses mukhammas written to the Navoi's 9-stanzas ghazal included in "Khazayin ul-Maoni"(Алишер Навоий, Тўла асарлар тўплами, 2011, 577), Andalib's 5-verses mukhammas written to the Navoi's 7-stanzas ghazal included in "Badoyi' ul-bidaya"(Алишер Навоий. Мукаммал асарлар тўплами. 1983, 388), Andalib's 7-verses mukhammas written to the Navoi's 7-stanzas ghazal included in "Badoyi' ul-bidaya"(Алишер Навоий. Мукаммал асарлар тўплами. 1983, 240), Andalib's 6-verses mukhammas written to the Navoi's 7-stanzas ghazal included in "Navodir un-nihoya"(Алишер Навоий. Мукаммал асарлар тўплами. 1983, 561), Andalib's 5-verses mukhammas written to the Navoi's 7-stanzas ghazal

included in "Badayi' ul-bidaya"(Алишер Навоий. Мукаммал асарлар тўплами. 1983, 370), Andalib's 5-verses mukhammas written to the Fuzuli's 5-stanzas ghazal(Муҳаммад Фузулий, Асарлар, 1968, 123), Andalib's 7-verses mukhammas written to the Fuzuli's 7-stanzas ghazal (Муҳаммад Фузулий, Асарлар, 1968, 286), Andalib's 5-verses mukhammmas written to the Ubaydi's ghazal and Andalib's 5-verses musamman written to the Navoi's 7-stanzas ghazal included in "Navodir un- nihoya"(Алишер Навоий, Мукаммал асарлар тўплами, 1983, 482-483).

In the third volume of the "History of Uzbek Literature" of 1978, information on the study of Andalib's life and work was recorded chronologically (Ўзбек адабиёти тарихи, 1978, 333-367). During the period until 1978, in this chrestomy, from foreign scientists: 1867 German Vamber "Chrestomy of Chigatoy literature", 1947 L. Klimovich "Chrestomy of the literature of the peoples of the USSR", 1947 N. Khojayeov "Andalib's " Foreword written to the epic "Layli and Majnun", 1963 B. Akhundov and A. Ulug'berdiyev, "Selected works of Andalib", 1973 Geldi Nazarov "Critical text of Andalib's epic "Yusuf and Zulaikha"" and in Uzbekistan In the first half of the 20th century, it was noted that there is information on the life and work of Andalib in the chrestomatization compiled by Fitrat, in 1958 by V. Abdullayev in his doctoral dissertation entitled "Uzbek literature in Khorezm in the 17th-18th centuries" and in other studies.

Moreover, it was also mentioned that Andalib has poems in manuscript bayazs numbered 1382, 1169, 1198, 1387, 7054, 299, 6759, 1103, 6973, 6998, 6985, 1155, 1188, 6993, 1918, which are stored in the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Andalib's saga "Zaynularab" was copied in the inventory numbered manuscript No. 384 and there is information about the copying of Andalib's "Chighir" radifil mukhammas in the manuscripts numbered C-162, 8.

There is information that the manuscript of Andalib, which begins with the verse "*Ey shahi nozik tabiat gul yuzingdin o'rgulay...*", is kept under inventory

number №3 in the manuscript fund of the Institute of Literature named after Makhtumkuli of the Turkmenistan Academy of Sciences.

In this chrestomathy, the following points are given regarding Andalib's contribution to translation studies: "From the works translated by Andalib, we know the epic "Mirzo Hamdam". The epic is written in the Tajik language, which is widely used among the peoples of Central Asia. This translated saga is currently stored in the manuscript fund of the UZR under inventory number №6895, it is said that it was copied in 1869 AD/1286 AH.

In conclusion, it can be said that Andalib's creativity and work have been widely studied in Uzbekistan and abroad. However, the scientific description of the manuscripts of the poet's works was not carried out as a special study. For this reason, special study of Andalib's works in the aspect of source studies and textual studies, determining the specific place of his colorful works in our classical literature is one of the important issues on the agenda.

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